

Women the Skilled Architect of the Society

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Abstract:- Women is empowered to be the skilled architect of the society. According to timeline health study of the status of women and her life expectancy has been steadily rising over the years, and the average life expectancy of a woman today is 80 years.

With this the fact that the women as the vital person in this living world, need arises to know the physiology and the different diseases by which a women suffer to prevent the future risks and complications.

As per a survey 61% of women presently are overweight, almost 26 % of them suffer with cardiovascular diseases and 23 % suffer with cancer. Other major health issues mostly are related with reproductive system, like menopausal symptoms and associated uterine fibroids and benign breast diseases.

Ayurveda, as the traditional medicine can equip the modern woman with its time-tested wisdom and help her to achieve optimal health of body, mind and spirit.

This article is an effort to understand women and her insights, for a better quality of living through ayurvedic principles.

Keywords:- Women health, Ayurveda, Traditional medicine.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Women – The Architect

The traditional system of medicine explains the tridosha and panchamahabhoota theory as the basis for ayurveda physiology. The scientific framework of the human body according to this ancient science involves the doshas, koshas, kalaas and different srotases in contributing to the biological system theory and physiological phase transitions. Women in this aspect is considered to be one of the indistinct from men, since she possess an extra set of srotas contributing to their biological heir through their physiological and structural co entity. The complex anatomical structure and physiology drives every women in different phases of life and results in many diseases when the prevention line is not under her control. Understanding these specific stages in the evolution of life, giving rise to new insights and helping in the development and growth is necessary to treat women on traditional lines.¹

¹ Hankey A. Ayurvedic physiology and etiology: Ayurvedo Amritanaam. The doshas and their functioning in terms of contemporary biology and physical chemistry. The Journal of Alternative & Complementary Medicine. 2001 Oct 1;7(5):567-74.

B. Importance Of Women and Vedic References

According to Hindu Purana, many of the Vedic references has its insight in giving women a prime role for her status and style of living. The religious scriptures like Vedas, Upanishads including great epics like Ramayana and Mahabharata depict the subtle truth of ancient Indian Science. Rigveda Samhita, Susruta Samhita, Charaka Samhita, Vagbhata Samhita, Manu Smritis, Puranas are the basic source of information to understand the social, domestic, economic, educational, religious and political status of women in ancient Indian history.²

History of cosmetology and beauty in ancient vedas is told in Purana, Ramayana, Mahabharata, Brihat Samhita and Vatsyayana Kamsutra which is one of the vital points to be considered in women life. Rigveda narrates the story of the bride Draupadi in the context of ‘Swayamvara’ as ‘Sairandhri’ apart from mentioning in Mahabharata highlighting the skills, beauty, ethnicity and elegant attitude of the women since ancient time.

Anushasana parva of mahabharata explains beauty and elegance for women by following few religious hymns and sacrifices along with pooja and vratas like chandrayana vrata in magasirsha masa. Atharvaveda highlights mantras for enhancing beauty. Garuda purana explains beautifying yogas for women with their benefits for a healthy life. Astanga sangraha & hridayakara enlists rodhradigana and eladigana as varnya, mukha lepa with their varjya and samyak prokta laksana according to ritu bheda for swasthyata of stri.³

C. Women physiology as a biological wonder

Amidst women, menstruation is the natural process which takes place every month in a chronological manner. This is described as Rajaswalaparicharya and the Menstrual blood (‘Raja’) also is a derivative of ‘Rasa Dhatu’. This process of menstrual cycle begins at the age of twelve years and stops at about fifty years of age. Another typical Physiology distinct to be understood in women is about Lactation. Breast-milk is formed out of ‘Rasa Dhatu’ (Ca. Ci. 15/17). The essential nutrient fraction of ‘Rasa Dhatu’, enters the breasts from the entire body and it is known as ‘Stanya’ (Su. Ni. 10/18). Development of Breasts: Ducts in the breast tissue of non-pregnant women are narrow and are constricted. During pregnancy and after delivery they get dilated as a natural phenomenon (Su. Ni. 10/16-17). There are various stimuli which needs to be understood in the case

² Punam, Dr & Sharma, Naina. (2017). The Role and Position of Women Ancient Society to Modern Society in India.

³ Mathur G. History and Position of Indian Women in Vedic Times: A Brief Discussion. Mumukshu Journal of Humanities. 2017 Dec;9(2):110-2.

of Breast-milk flow. Milk is ejected from the breasts because of touch, sight and even because of mere remembrance of the baby. Women as a whole is distinct because of possessing these extra features which serves for her biological Homeostasis.⁴

II. WOMEN CARE THROUGH AYURVEDA

The Ayurvedic term for the diseases of the female reproductive system is Guhyaroga. Garbhroga is the term for the diseases of the uterus. Embryology is known as Atulyagotriya. Diseases of the vagina (Yoni in Sanskrit) are called Yoni vyapat. There are 20 types of Yoni Vyapat listed in the Caraka Samhita and Astanga Hrdayam. 11 of these are Vata related, 2 Pitta, 1 Kapha and 6 involve multiple doshas.⁵

III. SKIN AND BEAUTY

The diseases are seen in the shareera due to the imbalance of the tridosha and as a consequence dhatu vaishmyata is seen. The Kapha dosha contributes for strength in the form of ojas and immunity. Pitta dosha takes care of the metabolic changes taking place in the body and hence regularise the nutritional aspects of skin. Vata as a whole is responsible for circulation of blood through all the skin layers and maintains the natural skin complexion and tone of the skin.

IV. DHATU AND ITS KARMA IN MAINTAINING THE SKIN

- Rasa Dhatu – Its main functioning being prenana, provides the subtle level nourishment and keeps the skin healthy by providing strength to the epithelial skin cells.
- Rakta Dhatu – Jeevana as its karma helps in detoxifying the blood and imparts natural colour to the skin with proper nourishment.
- Mamsa Dhatu – Lepana as its function, mamsa dhatu imparts firmness to skin and enhances skin integrity and hence loosening of the skin layers is prevented.
- Medho Dhatu – Snehana as its karma, provides the support with a sub cutaneous base and protects the skin from harsh and extreme climate.
- Asthi Dhatu – Dharana as its karma, renders good strength to teeth and nails. Kesha as the mala of asthi dhatu, gets its nourishment through Asthi and is maintained well.
- Majja Dhatu – Poorana is the main karma of Majja dhatu and it produces glossy hair and provides good tissue level compactness to the entire body.

- Shukra Dhatu – imparts vitality, strength, virility, luster, ojas and is the basis for reproduction.⁶

V. PCOD AND AYURVEDA

- Poly cystic ovarian disease and ayurveda interpreting that as medoja vikara with granthi vath lakshanas has explanation for dhatugata chikitsa. The cause for PCOD in Ayurveda is explained as if one is involved in mithyahara, possess beejadosha and pradushta arthava with daiva as a unknown factor too. Improper lifestyles and genetic factor along with obesity, hyperandrogeneism and high LH Secretion is considered to be the risk factors for PCOD.⁷
- Here the symptoms and cause can be understood with specific dosha predominance like Obesity, Infertility, and Hirsutism in Kapha Dosha. Hair loss, early baldness, premature greying, Painful menses, Acne formation in Pitta Pradhana Avastha. Painful menstruation with scanty menstrual blood flow and menstrual irregularities in Vata Pradhana Avastha.⁸
- Varuna is Kaphavata samaka, Pittavardhaka, Bhedana, Krimighna. Kanchanara is Gulmahara, Sothahara, Grandhahara, Kaphahara, Vranasodhaka. Guggulu is Vranaprakshalana, Lekhana, Rasayana, Saraka, Raktasodhaka, Tridoshaghna. Ashoka stimulates activity on the endometrium, ovary and contains phenolic-glycoside and non-phenolic glycosides helping in regularizing menstruation.⁹

VI. MENORRAGIA AND AYURVEDA

- Excessive menstrual bleeding along with body pain, back ache, burning sensation in groin and pelvic region discomfort is called as Asrigdhara in ayurveda termed as Menorrhagia.
- Uttara basti prayoga in this condition is useful to mitigate the harmful effects of vata dosha and regularises the menstrual cycle. Chandanadi, Rasnadi niruhabasti, Madhukadi anuvasanabasti, Kushadi asthapanabasti, Rodhradi asthapanabasti, Rasnadi asthapanabasti and Mustadi yapanabasti is widely practised. Prayoga of Pradirapu rasa, Bolaparpati, Gokshuradi Guggulu, Chandraprabhavati, Darvyadi Kashaya, Nyagrodha di Kashaya, Patrangasava,
- Lodhrasava, Ashokarista, Bruhath Kushmanda avaleha, Shalmali Ghrita, Mudgadya Ghrita, Sheetakalyanaka Ghrita, Shatapushpa taila, Pushyanuga choorna, Bhoomiamalaki choorna and Bolabaddha rasa which are

⁴ Patwardhan K. Concepts of human physiology in ayurveda. Sowardigpa and ayurveda', published by central Institute of higher Tibetan studies, sarnath, Varanasi. SamyakVak series-14. 2008:53-73.

⁵ P.V. Sharma, Caraka Samhita Vol II (Chowkambaka), Chapter XXX, Page 502, Verses 1-40; Prof. K.R. Srikantha Murthy, Astanga Hrdayam Vol 3 (Krishnadas Academy), Chapter 33, Page 310, Verses 27 B – 52 ½)

⁶ Chawardol SG, Jain SB, Natural Beauty Enhancer and Cosmetic Role of Ayurveda: A Review, Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics. 2019; 9(6-s):258-260 <http://dx.doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v9i6-s.3798>

⁷ Khot Bhagyashri et.al. Clinical efficacy of Ayurveda treatment on polycystic ovarian syndrome. Journal of pharmacy, 3(3): 21-25.

⁸ Chandak MK. A BRIEF REVIEW ON PCOD ACCORDING TO AYURVEDA AND MODERN.

⁹ K. Bharathi, C.M. Jain, B. Pushpalatha. Evaluation of Indigenous Drugs in the Management of PCOD in Teenage Girls. Int. J. Ayur. Pharma Research 2013; 1 (3): 30-35

Pitta shamaka, vatanulomaka, raktasthapaka, deepana and pachana are selected.¹⁰

VII. MENOPAUSAL SYNDROME AND AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT

Menopause is a natural process in a woman's life. It is a physical milestone in a woman's life. In early menopause, estrogen levels will decline rapidly, hence symptoms will appear with a sudden onset and lasts longer. The symptoms include hot flashes, headache, weight gain, depression, insomnia, mood swings, fuzzy thinking or fatigue. Prayoga of Ashwagandha, Arjuna, Ashoka, Shatavari is helpful in successful management of Menopausal Syndrome.¹¹

VIII. BREAST CANCER AND AYURVEDA

- The breast is formed by tissue including lobules, ducts and stroma with fat tissue. The breast cancer is the resultant of dushti seen in Rasa Dhatu. The common symptoms are presence of mass or lump in the breast. The other associated symptoms are swelling, tenderness, thickness, redness, nipple abnormalities, skin irritation and scarring.
- This cancer is classified into four grades based on the rate of cancer growth, axillary lymph node involvement, invasive spread and its area coverage with the metastatic rate.
- Cardamom helps in regulating the multiple processes involved in cancer like cell cycle, hormonal regulation, differentiation, apoptosis, inflammatory responses, DNA repair, and carcinogen metabolism and hence prevents breast cancer. Cardamom possesses anticancer benefits by regulating the immune system, it has manganese content at 80% percent of the recommended daily value and also small amounts of fiber and iron. Plenty of vitamin C, calcium, potassium, magnesium, and other nutrients cleanse the srotas and inhibits cancer.¹²
- Kanchanara Guggulu induced apoptotic cell death and possess antioxidant property helping in treating the cancer cases successfully. Amalaki, Latakaranja, Lakshmitaru possess antioxidant property and helps in prevention of further toxic cellular growth.¹³

¹⁰ Lakshmi, V. (2017). AYURVEDIC APPROACH OF MENORRHAGIA: ASRIGDARA. International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research, 5(6). Retrieved from <http://www.ijaprs.com/index.php/ijapr/article/view/694>

¹¹ Howkins & Bourne (2005), Shaw's a Textbook of Gynecology. Menopause, Reprinted, edit., Published by ELSEVIER, Pp. 56-67

¹² Vutakuri N, Somara S. Natural and herbal medicine for breast cancer using Elettaria cardamomum (L.) Maton. Int J Herbal Med. 2018;6(2):91-6.

¹³ Kulkarni P, Terwadkar MS, Kurmi K, Pingle MK, Phalle S, Irani MF. Cancer And Ayurveda. Deerghayu International; 2020 Nov 29.

IX. HERBAL ELIXIR AND THEIR PROPERTIES

- Glycyrrhiza glabra: Minimizes the production of tyrosinase to combat blackish discoloration which usually results in dark spots. It Removes excess melanin and brightens the skin. It is a potent antioxidant and controls oil production in the skin.¹⁴
- Curcuma longa: Essential oil derived from the rhizome of Curcumin longa (CL-EO) has marked anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anticancer, antiviral, and Antiseptic property. It improves complexion and Varnya in nature.¹⁵
- Rosa damascene: Anti -aging activity of Rosa damascene Mill by increasing the collagen content in human dermal fibroblast is proved in of the study. Skin glowing property and antimicrobial activity is analysed in studies where extract was tested for all the parts of the plant.¹⁶
- Ocimum sanctum: Tulsi gives luster to the skin, improves complexion, renders sweetness of voice and fosters beauty, intelligence and stamina. Tulsi also helps to prevent cancers caused by toxic compounds by reducing DNA damage and inducing apoptosis in precancerous and cancerous cells¹⁷
- Hibiscus rosa: Flowers of Hibiscus rosa-sinensis promotes hair growth and possess anti-greying properties. The leaves and flowers are observed to be promoters of hair growth and aid in healing of ulcers.¹⁸
- Saraca indica : Uterine tonic activity, Antioxytotic activity, Anticancer activity, Anti-inflammatory activity, Analgesic activity, Antiulcer activity, Antidiabetic activity, Immunomodulatory Activity, Antioxidant activity and Dermatoprotective property of Ashoka is

¹⁴ Sharma M, Sharma V, Sharma AK, Sharif S, Chaudhary M, Chowdhury RK, Dhillon A, Akil M. BEAUTY FACEPACK GLYCYRRHIZA GLABRA (YASHTIMADHU): A. DICKENSIAN. 2021;21(12).

¹⁵ Yating Zheng, Chunxing Pan, Zejun Zhang, Wenqian Luo, Xiaoxin Liang, Yaohui Shi, Linjie Liang, Xi Zheng, Lanyue Zhang, Zhiyun Du, Antiaging effect of Curcuma longa L. essential oil on ultraviolet-irradiated skin, Microchemical Journal, Volume 154, 2020, 104608, ISSN 0026-265X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2020.104608>.

¹⁶ Ahmed Y, Jamil SS, Hashimi A, Siraj MB, Jahangir U. Rosa Damascene Mill. (Rose): A versatile herb in cosmetology. TANG [HUMANITAS MEDICINE] [Internet]. 2019 Nov 29;9(4):2.1-2.4. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5667/TANG.2019.0017>

¹⁷ Cohen MM. Tulsi - Ocimum sanctum: A herb for all reasons. J Ayurveda Integr Med. 2014;5(4):251-259. doi:10.4103/0975-9476.146554

¹⁸ N Adhirajan, T Ravi Kumar, N Shanmugasundaram, Mary Babu, In vivo and in vitro evaluation of hair growth potential of Hibiscus rosa-sinensis Linn., Journal of Ethnopharmacology, Volume 88, Issues 2-3, 2003, Pages 235-239, ISSN 0378-8741, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741\(03\)00231](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-8741(03)00231)

proved, hence its useful in women and her systemic disorders. 19

X. DISCUSSION

In the present urban era, women pose a greater risk of threat to metabolic disorders and hormonal imbalance. COS, obesity, hypothyroidism are usually seen in 16- 20 yrs, in around age group 30-55yrs mainly diseases like Diabetes mellitus, Hypertension, Hypercholesterolemia, Coronary Heart disease are seen. After menopause other set of diseases like breast cancer, cervical cancer, osteoporosis can be observed. As metabolic disease pattern is different in different age groups, hence there is need of certain regiments which will act as prophylaxis for further disease enhancement. For this, life style modification and shodhana chikitsa along with herbal medicaments in their daily life is necessary.²⁰

XI. CONCLUSION

Women plays a vital role in functioning of life and she is considered to be the skilled architect of the society. Ayurveda offers guidelines and therapies not only to alleviate symptoms of menstrual disorders and diseases which women encounter in regular, but it brings regularity and balances the metabolism by understanding the root cause of the imbalances. All women have the power to heal within them. Ayurveda helps them to connect with their own inner wisdom and guidance and heal from within.

¹⁹ Nyeem MA, Haque MS, Haq MO, Nuruzzaman M, Uddin H, Islam BR. Ashoka (saraca indica) as women friendly plant: a review. National Journal of Advanced Research. 2017;3(2):3-7.

²⁰ Emerging metabolic disease in females: What Ayurveda can offer Shweta S. Deshpande Deepa S.ThamalAyurlog: National Journal of Research in Ayurved Science-2015; 3(3): 92-9